

EUROPEAN
**BIG DATA
VALUE** FORUM
3 - 5 NOVEMBER . 2020 - BERLIN + VIRTUAL

**European Big Data
Research for Industry.
3 projects. 7 sectors.
9 applications. 41 software
components. Now what?**

Focus Track 3: Market uptake: Bringing AI and Data Sciences to Practice - Parallel Session

Housekeeping rules for this session

- All participants except the speakers and the chairs will be muted by default during this session
- To ask a question, you can either use the Zoom Q&A panel or the Whova Q&A chat of this session or raise your hand
- The questions will be answered during the Q&A session or after of this session.
- Contact the session facilitator, Andrea Schillaci, if you have any technical issue

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Our project sponsors

Digital platform and analytic tools for energy

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BIG DATA VALUE
eCOSYSTEM PROJECT

Session Chairs

Despina Kopanaki
Project Manager,
FORTH-ICS

Jenny Rainbird
Senior Project Manager,
Inlecom Systems

Marieke Willems
Project Manager,
Trust-IT Services

CHAIRS

Invited Speakers

Toni Staykova
Co-Founder and Vice
President, UKeMED

Alon Rozen
Professor of Innovation,
Dean, Ecole des Ponts
Business School

Richard McCreadie
Lecturer in Information
Retrieval and Data Systems,
University of Glasgow

SPEAKERS

Agenda

- European Big Data Research for Industry. 3 projects. 7 sectors. 9 applications. 28 software components – Despina Kopanaki (FORTH)
- Now what? I-BiDaaS, Track & Know and BigDataStack explain & discuss – Marieke Willems (Trust-IT Services)
- Beyond 2020, contributing to the European Big Data ecosystem summary. Questions & Answers – Jenny Rainbird (Inlecom Systems)

3 projects. 1 synergy.

BigDataStack, I-BiDaaS and Track & Know joined forces at the BDV PPP Summit 2020 in a series of 9 online demos: the **Big Data Pilot Demo Days**.

3 projects. 3 years of research & innovation

After 3 years of research and innovation, I-BiDaaS, Track & Know and BigDataStack **join their forces** again in the **expert discussion** on the impact and uptake of Big Data research results.

The discussion will:

- Identify **shared barriers** to adoption of Big Data research in different sectors, and mechanisms to overcome these.
- Map the current and future **impact and sustainability** of their Big Data research
- Share best practices on the concrete **business questions** that have been answered in the **project pilots**

I-BiDaaS aims to empower IT and non-IT big data experts to easily utilize and interact with big data technologies.

- www.ibidaas.eu
- twitter.com/ibidaas
- [linkedin.com/in/i-bidaas](https://www.linkedin.com/company/i-bidaas)
- zenodo.org/communities/i-bidaas

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under grant agreement **No 780787**.

We made applications for **3 SECTORS**

- Financial
- Telecommunications
- Manufacturing

13 PARTNERS

10 USE CASES

11 SOFTWARE COMPONENTS

- 5 Open Source
- 6 Proprietary

Track & Know - Big Data for Mobility Tracking
Knowledge Extraction in Urban Areas - researches,
develops and exploits a new software framework
that aims at increasing the efficiency of Big Data.

- 🌐 www.trackandknowproject.eu
- 📘 TrackandKnow
- 🐦 @TrackandKnow
- 🌐 [linkedin.com/groups/12122105](https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12122105)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
Research and Innovation program under grant agreement **No 780754**.

We made
applications
for **3 SECTORS**

- Health Care
- Fleet management
- Motor insurance

14 PARTNERS

9 APPLICATIONS

**13 SOFTWARE
COMPONENTS**

All Open Source

BigDataStack is a unique high-powered stack of solutions with a focus on providing fully efficient and optimised processes across the complete set of technologies required by data operations and data-intensive applications.

- www.bigdatastack.eu
- [@BigDataStackEU](https://twitter.com/BigDataStackEU)
- [company/bigdatastack](https://www.linkedin.com/company/bigdatastack)
- ZENODO Search: [bigdatastack](https://zenodo.org/search?q=bigdatastack)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under grant agreement **No 779747**.

We made applications for **3 SECTORS**

- Retail
- Insurance,
- Shipping

PARTNERS

APPLICATIONS

SOFTWARE COMPONENTS

14 Open Source
3 Proprietary

Now you

- **To which of our stakeholder type do you belong?**
(Big Data Provider, Big Data Technology Provider, Manufacturing, Research & Academia, Standardisation Body, other)
- **Are you working with Big Data?**
(Yes, No)
- **Are you interested in Big Data Technologies to optimize your customer experience?**
(Yes, No, Maybe)
- **What is the main barrier or risk preventing you from implementing Big Data analytical solutions in your organization?**
(Costs, Lack of expertise, Uncertain Value (ROI))

How are we contributing to the European Big Data Ecosystem?

Alon Rozen

Professor of Innovation,
Dean, Ecole des Ponts
Business School

Richard McCreadie

Lecturer in Information
Retrieval and Data Systems,
University of Glasgow

What is the role/impact of new technologies in the industries? What barriers did you encounter with the industries in your project? How can we apply Big Data in businesses?

Toni Staykova

Co-Founder and Vice President, UKeMED

Richard McCreadie

Lecturer in Information Retrieval and Data Systems, University of Glasgow

Now What?

Alon Rozen

Professor of Innovation,
Dean, Ecole des Ponts
Business School

Toni Staykova

Co-Founder and Vice
President, UKeMED

Now What?

Stay tuned for our joint report with *recommendations on Big Data technologies ready to contribute to a European Big Data ecosystem, what's next?*

European Big Data Research for Industry

•3 Projects •7 Sectors •9 Applications •41 Software Components

Now what?

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- www.bigdatastack.eu
- [@BigDataStackEU](https://twitter.com/BigDataStackEU)
- [company/bigdatastack](https://www.linkedin.com/company/bigdatastack)
- [ZENODO Search: bigdatastack](https://zenodo.org/search?q=bigdatastack)

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Thank you!

